

STUDIES ON THE PRECIPITATION OF INVERTASE BY ALCOHOL-WATER MIXTURES

BY M. M. BISWAS

Yeast invertase has been precipitated at different pH values by ethanol-water mixtures consisting of 10 to 60% alcohol in the cold (at 0°-5°). At pH 4.5, the optimum pH for enzyme reaction of invertase, the influence of dissolved ions in the precipitation of the enzyme protein is also recognised. Although higher percentage of ethanol, viz., 60%, affords better yield of the precipitate, there is an optimum percentage of alcohol, viz., 50%, for precipitation of invertase of ideal activity at the optimum pH 4.5.

Influence of different salts on the invertase activity of yeast has been recorded in a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 815). The invertase preparations used for the experiments were made from samples of autolysed Brewer's yeast mixture after filtration with kieselguhr and subsequent dialysis. In this process the enzyme protein was not subjected to any further treatment for purification or crystallisation. The work of Cohn *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 459) regarding the fractionation of normal human plasma by precipitation with ethanol-water mixture in the cold suggested another practical method for purifying biologically active proteins. Their method eliminated the process of dialysis, necessary for the removal of ammonium sulphate, generally used for fractionation of the plasma. They removed the alcohol by evaporation under reduced pressure in the cold. The dangers of bacterial growth, which beset dialysis, are completely avoided in this method. An attempt has been made in the present investigation to crystallise the invertase protein from yeast extract according to this method, and some studies have been made on the protein-electrolyte interactions in presence of alcohol in the cold. The influence of pH on the optimum precipitation of the enzyme protein according to this new method has been studied.

An attempt has been made to correlate this optimum precipitation of the enzyme protein with the total invertase activity of the precipitate. The aim of the present series is to ascertain an optimum pH and percentage of alcohol for the crystallisation of invertase in the pure state with the maximum output of enzyme activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

The invertase extract was first prepared according to the method of Adams and Hudson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1959) by prolonging the period of autolysis to 4 days. Dried Brewer's yeast powder (220 g.) was treated with toluol (22 c.c.) and distilled water (330 c.c.), and the mixture was kept at 35° for 4 days. After this period of autolysis, the mixture was diluted with water (300 c.c.) and filtered with kieselguhr under suction. The clear filtrate was put to a dialyser at 35°, fed with running tap water and dialysis carried on for 48 hours, using toluol in the bags to prevent putrefaction. Percentage of protein in the invertase filtrate was found to

be 1.39. The enzyme extract (10 c.c.) was mixed with 40 c.c. mixtures of ethanol and water. Percentage of ethanol varied from 10.0 to 60.0. Precipitation was made in the cold in the frigidaire, the temperature of which varied between 0° and 5°. Precipitate, after filtration under suction in the cold, was dried in vacuum and weighed as such. The specimen, so obtained, is likely to contain different types of proteins, both active and inactive, but otherwise the material is of sufficient purity and the observed behaviour relates to this purified specimen as a whole. Experiments were performed in a range of pH varying between 3.5 and 7.0. The results have been recorded in Table I (A-F). Precipitates of the various protein-alcohol mixtures were centrifuged and after decantation of the supernatant liquid tested for their enzyme activity in the usual manner. The pH values between 3.5 and 7.0 and the percentages of alcohol between 10.0 and 60.0 were correlated with the invertase activity of 10 g. invertase extract in each case. The results are recorded in Table II and in Fig. 1.

TABLE I

Invertase extract : 10 c.c. Alcohol-water mixture : 40 c.c.

Protein precipitated at different pH.

% EtOH.	A. pH 3.5.	B. pH 4.0.	C. pH 4.5.	D. pH 5.0.	E. pH 6.0.	F. pH 7.0.
10.0	0.0044 g.	0.0117 g.	0.0031 g.	0.0030 g.	0.0030 g.	0.0158 g.
15.0	0.0092	0.0294	0.0080	0.0100	0.0140	0.0154
20.0	0.0096	0.0302	0.0080	0.0132	0.0138	0.0174
25.0	0.0064	0.0310	0.0144	0.0210	0.0132	0.0166
30.0	0.0130	0.0340	0.0162	0.0244	0.0148	0.0132
35.0	0.0122	0.0340	0.0122	0.0246	0.0190	0.0160
40.0	0.0168	0.0280	0.0166	0.0270	0.0128	0.0160
50.0	0.0342	0.0446	0.0380	0.0652	0.0594	0.0728
60.0	0.0420	0.0514	0.0550	0.0706	0.0744	0.0904

TABLE II

Invertase activity at different percentages of alcohol and pH values.

Invertase extract used : 10 c.c. (% protein = 1.39).

Substrate : 80 g. sucrose in 200 c.c. water.

Invertase activity in g. glucose by 10 g. yeast extract at diff. pH values.

% EtOH.	pH 3.5.	pH 4.0.	pH 4.5.	pH 5.0.	pH 6.0.	pH 7.0.
10.0	27.7	89.9	109.4	98.7	89.9	85.2
15.0	29.7	86.1	112.3	107.9	95.2	87.07
20.0	29.9	98.7	147.2	119.04	107.9	89.9
25.0	29.7	103.7	161.8	126.5	109.4	91.9
30.0	31.1	107.9	161.8	139.5	115.6	98.7
35.0	33.7	112.3	168.6	144.6	119.04	101.1
40.0	35.1	119.04	176.05	150.0	122.6	103.7
50.0	36.7	122.6	231.4	155.8	126.5	109.4
60.0	36.7	124.5	231.4	161.8	130.6	112.5

DISCUSSION

Influence of H^+ -ion concentration on the precipitation of enzyme protein from a solution of invertase from Brewer's yeast by alcohol has been recorded in Table I. To avoid denaturation of the precipitated protein, cold conditions have been maintained (0° - 5°). Cohn *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) carried out their experiments on fractionation of human plasma in a comparatively cold zone (0° - 10°). The condition of precipitation is, however, quite satisfactory in the present instance. The range of H^+ -ion concentration varies between pH 3.5 and 7.5 and that of ethanol concentration, between 10.0% and 60.0%. Evidently the optimum precipitation of enzyme protein has been observed in the protein-alcohol mixture at pH 4.5. It may be noted that only two variables have been studied in the protein precipitation reactions. These are the ethanol concentration and the H^+ -ion concentration. It is evident from Table I that in the range of ethanol concentrations between 10% and 40%, the amount of protein precipitation is rather low, whereas at 50% and 60% concentrations of alcohol, the amounts of the precipitate are appreciably high.

FIG. 1

Fig. 1 (vide Table II) illustrates the variation of invertase activity of enzyme extracts with the percentage of alcohol used for precipitation of the enzyme at pH values ranging between 3.5 and 7.0. It is evident from the steepness of the curve at pH 4.5 that for the same percentage of alcohol used, precipitates at this pH possess superior invertase activity. Enzyme activity, as measured in terms of g. glucose formed by 10 g. of invertase extract, attains almost a maximum at this pH (4.5) and at 50% alcohol strength. It is significant that at pH 4.5, the influence of dissolved ions in the precipitation of the enzyme protein has already been recognised. The

present experiments establish beyond doubt that mere precipitation is not the criterion of activity, and the activity of the precipitate is not proportional to the mass. Thus, it is apparent from Table II that activity increases by about one-third its value with increase of percentage of alcohol from 10.0 to 60.0. Alcohol precipitation figures (vide Table I) indicate that amount of protein precipitate increases in some cases about twenty times for the above range (10.0% to 60.0% alcohol). It is therefore possible from the present series of investigations to contemplate an optimum pH (4.5) as also an optimum percentage of alcohol (50.0) for precipitation of invertase of ideal activity.

Thanks of the author are due to Sri N. Adhikari, M.Sc., Manager, Bengal Chemical & Pharmaceutical Works Ltd., for the active encouragement during the progress of the work.

PRAFULLA CHANDRA RESEARCH LABORATORY,
BENGAL CHEMICAL & PHARMACEUTICAL WORKS LTD.,
CALCUTTA-11.

Received August 16, 1959.